

Investigations on the Behaviour of Potassium *n*-Butyl Xanthate and Benzamidothiosemicarbazide at D.M.E.

M. M. ANSARI, M. C. JAIN and WAHID U. MALIK*

Department of Chemistry, S. D. College, Muzaffar Nagar-251 001, (U. P.)

Manuscript received 31 March 1979, accepted 9 July 1980

Potassium *n*-butyl xanthate (PNBX) and benzamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) were studied at d.m.e. The polarographic studies carried out on the behaviour of PNBX and BTSC consist of the effect of concentration, *pH*, supporting electrolytes and mercury column heights. These waves were found to be diffusion controlled. In case of PNBX, $E_{1/2}$ (-0.22 volts) remained constant with the increase in *pH*, while in case of BTSC $E_{1/2}$ increased continuously with the increase in *pH*. Besides the studies on reversibility of the process, logarithmic analysis of the wave yielded straight lines with mean slope ratio of 0.033 volts (PNBX) and 0.032 volts (BTSC), showing reversible and two electron transfer process. The *pK* value (8.0) of BTSC has been evaluated from *pH* vs $-E_{1/2}$ plot. The mechanism of the dimerisation of these compounds has been proposed.

THE polarographic behaviour of a number of sulphur compounds such as thiols, sulphhydryl, cysteine, cystine, thiolactic acid^{1,2} has been investigated in recent years. Compounds such as dithiocarbaminocarboxylic acid³, thioglycolic acid^{4,5}, dithiocarbamate^{6,7} and glutathione^{8,9} showed anodic depolarization which was accompanied by salt formation, the general electrode process may be represented by the following equation

The electrode process is generally irreversible but in a few cases like the anodic depolarization of glutathione the reversibility of the process has been reported.

The electrode process does not merely depend on the nature and chemical composition of the adsorbate but is also highly dependent on the difference in crystalline orientation in the film of mercury salt. Thus it is clear that the conditions of forming adsorbate changes with the type of compound involved, e.g. cysteine showed the adsorption effect between *pH* 2-9, whereas glutathione gave a diffusion controlled wave directly proportional to concentration at least upto $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in the whole *pH* range.

In floatation of sulphide minerals as xanthates the research workers and mill operators have long desired, a rapid method of xanthate determination, because most of the existing methods are long time consuming on account of the impurities which are invariably present in the floatation liquors. Therefore a detailed polarographic study of the behaviour of potassium *n*-butyl xanthate may prove useful in the feasibility of the polarographic method for its

estimation in the presence of impurities. Another sulphur containing ligand benzamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) on account of its dual bonding sites nitrogen and sulphur showed potentiality as a good analytical reagent for metal estimation. Therefore, with a view to obtain information about the applicability of polarographic method in the study of metal-BTSC reaction, its behaviour has been studied at d.m.e. The information gathered during these studies are reported in this communication.

Materials and Methods :

Potassium *n*-butyl xanthate (hereafter designated as PNBX) and benzamidothiosemicarbazide (hereafter designated as BTSC) were synthesized and their purity was checked by chemical analysis. Fresh solution of PNBX in air free conductivity water and of BTSC in ethyl alcohol-water mixture was always used. All the other chemicals used viz. KCl, KNO₃, NaOH, Na₂B₄O₇·10H₂O, HCl, HClO₄, CH₃COONa, CH₃COOH etc. were of B.D.H. 'AR' grade and their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Fresh solution of 0.2% gelatin used as maximum suppressor in these experiments, was prepared in warm water to avoid effect of ageing. Doubly distilled air free conductivity water was used in all the experiments.

A Toshniwal manual polarograph in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer (sensitivity 1 : 1, 1 : 10, 1 : 100) was used to record polarographic curves. The polarograph contained saturated calomel electrode connected to a cell through a salt bridge in conjunction with a d.m.e. having following characteristics, $m=1.942$ mg/sec ; drop time $t=2.5$ sec ; at the height of mercury column $h=40$ cm. Triply distilled mercury was used for d.m.e. The inert

* Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee.

atmosphere was maintained by passing purified nitrogen gas for about 15 minutes to ensure complete deaeration. pH metric measurements were carried out by Elico-pH meter model C₁₀ India after allowing sufficient warming up period and standardizing with standard phthalate buffer (pH=4) and borax buffer (pH=9.2).

The following sets of the solution were prepared to study the polarographic behaviour of the PNBX and BTSC at d.m.e. In each set 2.0 ml of 2M KCl and 2.0 ml of 0.2% gelatin were added before making required volume.

(i) *Effect of concentration of PNBX and BTSC in 0.16M KCl :*

1.0 ml, 2.0 ml, 3.0 ml, 4.0 ml, 5.0 ml each of 0.025M PNBX and BTSC were diluted to 25.0 ml with water (Table 1)

Concentration $\times 10^{-3}M$	$i_d(\mu A)$		i_d/C	
	PNBX	BTSC	PNBX	BTSC
1.0	0.400	0.299	0.400	0.299
2.0	0.788	0.620	0.394	0.310
3.0	1.121	0.903	0.373	0.301
4.0	1.620	1.192	0.405	0.298
5.0	1.987	1.590	0.397	0.318

(ii) *Effect of concentration of PNBX and BTSC in 0.16M KNO₃ :*

1.0 ml, 2.0 ml, 3.0 ml, 4.0 ml, 5.0 ml, each of 0.025M PNBX and BTSC were diluted to 25.0 ml with water.

(iii) *Effect of pH :*

2.0 ml of 0.025 M PNBX solution was made upto 25.0 ml by the addition of suitable buffers of different pH ranging from 7.7 to 10.5 ; and 3.0 ml of 0.025 M BTSC solution was made upto 25.0 ml

by the addition of suitable buffers of different pH ranging from 4.0 to 12.0. KCl and gelatin were added as usual before making the required volume (Table 2).

(iv) *Effect of heights of mercury column :*

1.0 ml each of 0.025 M of PNBX and BTSC was made upto 25.0 ml with water (Table 3).

Sl. No.	h_{eff} (cm)	$h_{eff}^{1/2}$	PNBX		BTSC	
			$i_d(\mu A)$	i_d/h_{eff}	$i_d(\mu A)$	i_d/h_{eff}
1.	30	5.48	0.310	0.010	0.299	0.009
2.	40	6.32	0.420	0.010	0.380	0.009
3.	50	7.07	0.520	0.010	0.453	0.009
4.	60	7.75	0.600	0.010	0.522	0.008

Results and Discussion

Current voltage curves of PNBX and BTSC gave current directly proportional to concentration ranging $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ and a linear relation was obtained between i_d and concentration of PNBX and BTSC (Table 1, Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Plot of i_d vs concentration.

TABLE 2—RESULTS FROM THE LOGARITHMIC ANALYSIS OF THE WAVES IN DIFFERENT BUFFERS (Fig. 2. Curves 1-6) and (Fig. 3. Curves 1-9)

Sl. No.	PNBX				BTSC			
	pH	$i_d(\mu A)$	$-E_{1/2}(V)$	Slope(V)	pH	$i_d(\mu A)$	$-E_{1/2}(V)$	Slope(V)
1.	7.7	2.110	0.22	0.036	4.0	0.901	0.123	0.028
2.	8.7	2.010	0.22	0.030	4.8	0.901	0.138	0.035
3.	9.0	1.850	0.22	0.034	5.5	0.891	0.160	0.029
4.	9.5	1.510	0.22	0.027	7.0	0.901	0.190	0.030
5.	10.0	1.282	0.22	0.031	8.0	0.901	0.220	0.035
6.	10.5	1.131	0.22	0.040	9.2	0.850	0.232	0.033
7.	—	—	—	—	10.5	0.860	0.240	0.035
8.	—	—	—	—	11.3	0.890	0.251	0.039
9.	—	—	—	—	12.0	0.890	0.260	0.032

The half-wave potential $E_{1/2} = -0.22$ volt (PNBX) and $E_{1/2} = -0.1$ volt (BTSC) of the waves at various concentrations remained constant. Approximately it can be taken as a criterion of reversibility of the wave.

Well defined anodic waves were obtained between pH 7.7-10.5 in case of PNBX (Fig. 2, Curves 1-6) and between pH 4.0 to 12.0 in case of BTSC (Fig. 3, Curves 1-9). All the plots of $\log \frac{i_d - i}{1}$ vs $-E_{d.e.}$, yielded straight lines with mean slope ratio 0.033 V (PNBX) and 0.0326 V (BTSC), showing reversible and two electron transfer process (Table 2). From the data it is clear that the half wave potential remained constant in case of PNBX while it is shifted to more negative values with increasing pH in case of BTSC. In case of PNBX, i_d decreases with increasing pH, however i_d remained constant in case of BTSC.

Fig. 4. Plot of pH vs $E_{1/2}$

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on Polarographic Behaviour of PNBX.

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on Polarographic Behaviour of BTSC.

recorded at different heights of mercury column. In both the cases, well defined anodic waves were obtained over the whole range. A linear plot of i_d vs $h_{eff}^{1/2}$ (Table 3, Fig. 5) showed that the reaction was diffusion controlled in both the cases.

Fig. 5. Plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{eff}}$

In case of BTSC, the plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH gave straight line upto pH 8.0 (Table 2, Fig. 4). The intersection of these lines gave the value of dissociation constant (pK_1) 8.0.

A series of polarograms of PNBX and BTSC, both at fixed concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) were

Usually sulphur containing organic compounds such as thioureas, cystein etc., gave anodic waves resulting in the formation of mercury sulphides and the reactions have been shown one electron transfer.

A mechanism involving dimerisation of PNBX and BTSC is proposed explaining the two electron

transfer reaction

(PNBX)

References

1. R. S. SAXENA and P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 1149.
2. R. S. SAXENA and P. SINGH, *Zeit. Naturforschung*, 1969, **24(B)**, 1520.
3. R. ZAHRADNIK, *Chem. Listy.*, 1955, **49**, 1002.
4. D. L. LEUSSING and I. M. KOLTHOFF, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1953, **100**, 334.
5. G. SARTORI, A. LIBERTI and C. CALZOLARI, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1950, **20**, 97.
6. E. C. GREGG and W. P. TAYLOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **72**, 4561.
7. G. SARTORI and C. CALZOLARI, *Chem. Abst.*, 1952, **46**, 6958.
8. D. M. COULSON, W. R. CROWELL and S. L. FRIESS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, **22**, 525.
9. W. STRICKS and I. M. KOLTHOFF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4646.